

Title: Brazil’s Benthic Habitat Map is the Government’s official Marine Spatial Planning tool		
Target End-Users: (1) Interministerial Commission for the Resources of the Sea (CIRM), Ministry of the Environment and Climate Change; (2) Brazilian Ministry of Mining and Energy ; (3) Marine Spatial Planning Technical Teams.		
Period when the underpinning research was undertaken: 2020 - 2026		
Details of staff conducting the underpinning research from the submitting unit:		
Name(s):	Role(s) (e.g. job title):	Period active in the project:
Vitor de Souza Jarbas Bonetti Tiago Gandra	Senior Researchers, UFSC South Brazilian Shelf Case Study Group	2020-2026
Luis Conti	Senior Researcher, USP	2020-2026
Ibon Galparsoro	Senior Researcher, AZTI (Spain)	2020-2026
Marinez Scherer as lead of the UFSC Group	Marinez Scherer is the Leader of Mission Atlantic South Brazilian Shelf Case Study & Marine Spatial Planning and Integrated Coastal Zone Management Coordinator at the Brazilian Ministry of the Environment and Climate Change (2023-2024)	2020-2026
Period when the claimed impact occurred: 2024-2026		

1 Summary of Outcome / Impact

The work was developed within the [EU Horizon 2020 Mission Atlantic](#) project, which aims to improve integrated Atlantic Ocean management through advanced data systems and planning tools. Within this framework, the project produced the first comprehensive broad-scale **benthic habitat map** of the Brazilian continental margin, covering approximately 5 million km² across the Brazilian Exclusive Economic Zone (EEZ) and Extended Continental Shelf.

Using the [EUNIS habitat classification system](#) and integrating multiple open-access environmental datasets, the study identified the spatial distribution of benthic habitats across three major marine ecoregions of Brazil.

The results were operationalised beyond the scientific publication by integrating the habitat layers into the Brazilian [SeaSketch Marine Spatial Planning](#) platform (www.seasketch.org/brasil/app), allowing dissemination of the operational product to R&D and Policy Communities in 2024-2026.

This integration enables planners, policymakers, and stakeholders to overlay human activities with habitat distribution and ecosystem services, automatically generating reports that identify:

- the geographic footprint of activities
- the benthic habitats affected
- the associated ecosystem services potentially impacted

By transforming scientific outputs into interactive decision-support tools, the project directly supports ecosystem-based Marine Spatial Planning (MSP) in Brazil.

Mission Atlantic also advanced the collection, harmonisation, and systematisation of multiple spatial layers related to maritime activities. Together with the habitat maps, these datasets now constitute one of the most up-to-date spatial databases available to support MSP at the national scale. These layers are hosted in the SeaSketch platform and have been used by regional planners to guide the early stages of Brazil’s Marine Spatial Planning process. In particular, the MSP Pilot Project in South Brazil adopted the produced maps as the official characterization of

benthic habitats for the planning process.

The maps were presented in multiple public technical interactions and demonstrated to the Brazilian [Ministry of the Environment and Climate Change](#) beyond the MSP initiative.

It was also discussed in the context of the governmental program REVIMAR. During early planning discussions, REVIMAR opted to use the resulting publication as a scientific reference for developing a national benthic habitat classification system. The outputs were presented during the first expert workshop and are now intended to support the development of a national standard for benthic habitat classification. As a result, a consultancy agreement with [Vitor de Souza](#) was established to provide scientific advisory throughout the process.

News Release on Official REVIMAR Project Launch, <https://www.gov.br/mma/pt-br/noticias/mma-lanca-programa-para-fortalecer-gestao-marinha-do-pais-baseada-em-evidencias> (Source: Comissão Interministerial para os Recursos do Mar <https://www.marinha.mil.br/secirm/pt-br>)

The maps have also been presented (2025-2026) in discussions with the Brazilian [Ministry of Mining and Energy](#) in the context of early planning for offshore wind development, so that they are considered as a reference layer to support environmental characterization and spatial planning of offshore energy activities.

2 Underpinning research

CONTEXT:

The South Brazilian Shelf Case Study collaboration between EU and BR teams, delivered a Benthic Habitat Map and Classification System, that directly resulted in spin-off national R&D that closed the Science-2-Policy Gap.

REVIMAR – XI PSRM: a direct spin-off of MISSION ATLANTIC and bridging the Science-2-Policy Gap

<https://www.marinha.mil.br/secirm/sites/www.marinha.mil.br/secirm/files/2025-03/XI-PSRM.pdf>

The XI Sectoral Plan for Marine Resources is a document designed by the Interministerial Commission for Marine Resources to guide mid-term priorities for Brazilian Government. One of the objectives outlined is to develop and establish the *REVIMAR (Assessment, Monitoring and Conservation of Marine Biodiversity)* Research program.

In this context, Mission Atlantic output directly contributed to the goal to “*Establish the scientific basis and integrated actions capable of supporting policies, actions and strategies for conservation of marine biodiversity and the sustainable use of living marine resources*”.

More specifically, the Benthic Habitat Map developed will potentially contribute to Brasil's National Plan Milestone 5.2.2.a "identify strategies for generating, integrating and sharing data and information from biodiversity and marine living resources monitoring programs and projects, through workshops with the participation of experts and managers (SDG14.a)".

REVIMAR 1st expert workshop on habitat classification. Brasilia, 30 Oct 2025
(Credits: Vitor de Souza)

Concurrent BR Initiatives represented at REVIMAR Expert Workshop, 30 Oct 2025

Source: <https://www.marinha.mil.br/secirm/pt-br>

3 References to the research:

- De Souza, Vitor, Ibon Galparsoro, Tiago B. Gandra, Luis A. Conti, Marinez E. Scherer, and Jarbas Bonetti. 2025. "Charting the Uncharted: Broad-Scale Benthic Habitat Distribution in the Brazilian Continental Margin." *Estuarine, Coastal and Shelf Science*, February, 109203. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ecss.2025.109203>
- De Souza, Vitor; Gandra, Tiago; Bonetti, Jarbas ; Galparsoro, Ibon; Conti, Luis; Scherer, Marinez. 2024. "Benthic habitats using EUNIS classification for the Brazilian EEZ", Mendeley Data, V1, <https://doi.org/10.17632/2mvy9bgrxs.1>
- Scherer, M. E., Sardinha, G. D., de Souza, V., Gandra, T. B., Floeter, S. R., Liedke, A. M., ... & Gasalla, M. A. 2024. Under pressure: an integrated assessment of human activities and their potential impact on the ecosystem components of the Southern Brazilian continental

4 Details of the IMPACT NARRATIVE:

In parallel to delivery of the first Benthic Habitat Map & Classification System for the breadth of the BR Shelf, Prof. Marinez Scherer was recruited to coordinate Coastal Management Integration Group (GIGERCO, CIRM) within the Ministry of Environment & Climate Change.

This helped form a FOCUS GROUP of policy professional end-users in the Ministry office in Brazil, that could be trained using the Marine Spatial Planning tool [SeaSketch.org](https://seasketch.org) developed by UCLA (USA). The Integration Group is a core end-user cohort charged with implementing MSP and MPA designation along the SBS South Brazilian Shelf. A tangible output of the project is that this Pilot area in Brazil was selected for implementation directly because of the activities in MISSION ATLANTIC in data harmonization.

End-users committed to continued capacity building, based on other mature IEA Tools & Products, integration of “*fit-for-purpose*” input by end-users, and documenting direct added value to regional policy makers in implementation of MSPs and MPA objectives.

Early proxies of added-value and long-term impact included publishing the first broad-scale habitat map with full-coverage for the Brazilian Exclusive Economic Zone (EEZ) in a peer-reviewed journal (Estuarine Coastal and Shelf Science, 2025) and making it available (Mendeley Data, 2024; [SeaSketch.org](https://seasketch.org) platform), which have been used by policymakers.

The results are now being used as the conceptual framework for the [REVIMAR Ocean Research program](#), under the Brazilian Ministry of Environment coordination. The research output is being used to guide the creation of a regional Habitat Classification System that will be adopted in Brazil, Argentina and Uruguay [Pers. Comm. [Rafael Sperb, REVIMAR coordinator](#)]. Based on the work, a research proposal funded by Global Environment Funding (UNEP/GEF) in Jun 2025, and implemented 2026-2029 will harmonize benthic habitat monitoring protocols to enable the transboundary implementation of sustainable management measures in the Southwest Atlantic Large Marine Ecosystem (LME) that spans Brasil-Uruguay-Argentina¹.

We were also able to provide key information for ecosystem-based management to high-level agencies (e.g. Ministry of Environment, [Interministerial Commission for Marine Resources](#), Ministry of Energy², Danish Energy Agency³). This supports the Marine Spatial Planning efforts that are being developed regionally to advance definition of sensitive areas, priority for conservation and environmental suitability for specific sectors [Pers. Comm. with [João Luiz Nicolodi](#), Coordenador-Geral (FCE 1.13) Ministério do Meio Ambiente e Mudança do Clima.

SCALE & REACH: The Benthic Habitat Map, and extended work through nationally funded REVIMAR, involved much greater diversity of BR National Initiatives and stakeholders, than the EU funded project could have done on its own.

Appointment of Marinez Scherer as Marine Spatial Planning and Integrated Coastal Zone Management Coordinator at the Brazilian Ministry of the Environment and Climate Change (2023-2024) deepen trust, frequency of capacity building engagement, and policy end-user uptake of the Benthic Habitat Map, as **a critical asset** for Marine Spatial Planning along the BR Shelf. Although serendipitous, and beyond Consortium control, this opportunity is likely to place the

¹ Proposal funded by GEF, 6 Jun 2025, to extend MISSION ATLANTIC Benthic Habitat Maps: [Foster transboundary cooperation and capacities for the management of the marine biodiversity of the Southwest Atlantic Large Marine Ecosystems through regional and national actions | GEF](#) GEF Project ID 11476

² Presentation delivered at a private event with representatives from the Ministry of Environment and the Ministry of Energy. Date: September/2024

³ Danish Energy Agency requested demonstrations of the Benthic Habitat Map potential for licensing offshore energy projects (24 Oct 2024; Marinez Scherer as representative)

project outputs on a secure path to long-term impact.

Early proxy evidence of **systematic reach**, is citation of the peer-review work by UNESCO (2025) and Ireland Policy Documents (2024), as well as statement by Gilberto Sales, Ministry of Environment and Climate Change, that the “*Benthic Habitat Map is considered the official map to be used for licensing purposes (oil and gas, offshore wind energy)*”.

5. Sources/ Evidence to corroborate the impact:

- Brazil Shelf Benthic Maps and Classification System embedded in [SeaSketch.org](https://www.seasketch.org) as a Case Study and working Decision Support Tool for outreach to Ministerial stakeholders

<https://www.seasketch.org/brasil/app/overlays>

- Overview of the Ministerial Stakeholder Engagement in Brasil in 2024-2025 was captured in a 5 min video on the [MISSION ATLANTIC You Tube Channel](#).

- As of March 2026 “*benthic habitat map is considered the official map to be used for*

licensing purposes, environment impact assessment (oil and gas, offshore wind energy), marine spatial planning, marine protected areas” Gilberto Sales (Director of the Department for the Co-Management of Fisheries Resources - Ministry of Environment and Climate Change.

EVIDENCE OF POLICY CITATIONS:

- [Avaliação rápida do MSPglobal para o planejamento espacial marinho no Brasil](#) UNESCO, 1 Jan 2025

Broad-scale benthic habitat classification of the South Atlantic
 Kirsty A. McQuaid et al. (2023) *Progress in Oceanography*
 Authors from Universidade Federal de Santa Catarina are Jarbas Bonetti and Vitor de Souza
 The matching author names were Vitor de Souza

“ No que tange a mapeamento de habitats marinhos, métodos foram adaptados e testados em iniciativas acadêmicas (de Souza et al., 2025 ; McQuaid et al., 2023). ”
 On page 21

McQuaid, K. A., Bridges, A. E. H., Howell, K. L., Gandra, T. B. R. et al. 2023. Broad-scale benthic habitat classification of the South Atlantic. *Progress in Oceanography* 214, 103016 <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.pocean.2023.103016>
 On page 30

- Annual Report 2023/Tuarascáil Bhlíantúil 2023 (English and Irish/Bilingual versions) Marine Institute (Ireland) 19 Jul 2024

Broad-scale benthic habitat classification of the South Atlantic
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McQuaid, K. A., Bridges, A. E., Howell, K. L., Gandra, T. B., de Souza, V., Currie, J. C., ... Furey, T., ... Yool, A. 2023. Broad-scale benthic habitat classification of the South Atlantic. *Progress in oceanography*, 214, 103016. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.pocean.2023.103016>
 On page 62 of PDF #1

6. Impact Pathway for 2026-2030:

- 2026: External Evaluation of Impact, by Saskia Walcott (Walcott Communications)
- 2026: Monitor Policy Citations, to steer Comms Strategy for REVIMAR & GEF LME Project
- 2027: Train Brazilian partners how to track Evidence of Impact
- 2027: Transfer Impact Narrative to REVIMAR/GEF projects, to monitor long-term impact of the Benthic Habitat Map & Classification System within various Ministries

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